

Trimethylamine N-oxide impairs pyruvate and fatty acid oxidation in cardiac mitochondria

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Graphical Abstract

TMAO impairs mitochondrial energy metabolism in the heart

- Increase in the severity of cardiovascular events
- Exacerbation of the progression of cardiovascular disease

Highlights:

- Trimethylamine-N-oxide (TMAO) impairs β -oxidation in cardiac mitochondria.
- TMAO decreases pyruvate metabolism via impaired substrate flux.
- Increased TMAO content induces energy metabolism disturbances in the heart.
- Increased TMAO concentration is a risk factor for heart failure progression.

Abstract

Increased plasma concentration of trimethylamine N-oxide (TMAO), a proatherogenic metabolite, has been linked to adverse cardiovascular outcomes; however, it remains unclear whether TMAO is a biomarker or whether it induces direct detrimental cardiovascular effects. Because altered cardiac energy metabolism and mitochondrial dysfunction play crucial roles in the development of cardiovascular diseases, we hypothesized that increased TMAO concentration may alter mitochondrial energy metabolism. The aim of the present study was to determine the effects of TMAO on cardiac mitochondrial energy metabolism.

Acute exposure of cardiac fibers to TMAO decreased LEAK (substrate-dependent) and OXPHOS (oxidative phosphorylation-dependent) mitochondrial respiration with pyruvate and impaired substrate flux via pyruvate dehydrogenase. The administration of TMAO at a dose of 120 mg/kg for 8 weeks increased TMAO concentration in plasma and cardiac tissues 22-23 times to about 15 μ M and 11 nmol/g, respectively. Long-term TMAO administration decreased mitochondrial LEAK state respiration with pyruvate by 30% without affecting OXPHOS state respiration. However, no significant changes in mitochondrial reactive oxygen species production were observed after acute exposure of cardiac fibers to TMAO under physiological conditions. In addition, both long-term TMAO administration and acute exposure to TMAO decreased respiration with palmitoyl-CoA indicating impaired β -oxidation.

Taken together, our results demonstrate that increased TMAO concentration impairs pyruvate and fatty acid oxidation in cardiac mitochondria. Thus, the accumulation of TMAO in cardiac tissues leads to disturbances in energy metabolism that can increase the severity of cardiovascular events.

Abbreviations

ETS capacity - electron transfer system capacity; FCR - flux control ratio; LEAK respiration – substrate-dependent respiration; OXPHOS respiration - ADP-stimulated, oxidative phosphorylation dependent; ROS - reactive oxygen species; ROX - residual oxygen consumption; TMAO - trimethylamine N-oxide.

Keywords: trimethylamine N-oxide, cardiac mitochondria, energy metabolism, reactive oxygen species

1. Introduction

Cardiovascular diseases are a leading cause of death worldwide (Okwuosa et al., 2016; WHO, 2014). The link between diet and the risk of cardiovascular disease is well-established (Brunner et al., 2008; Dehghan et al., 2012), and recent clinical studies regarding the independent association of the intestinal microbiota-dependent metabolite trimethylamine N-oxide (TMAO) with the incidence of major adverse cardiovascular events (Tang et al., 2013; Wang et al., 2011) have provided novel insight into the role of diet in the development of cardiovascular diseases.

TMAO is a product of the intestinal metabolism of dietary L-carnitine, choline and phosphatidylcholine. Despite that TMAO may protect cells by acting as osmolyte and stabilizing protein folding (Ufnal et al., 2015), growing evidence suggests that plasma TMAO concentration is a marker of cardiovascular risk (Tang et al., 2013; Troseid et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2011). TMAO has been shown to promote atherosclerosis and to be associated with cardiovascular risks (Koeth et al., 2013; Wang et al., 2011). It has been demonstrated that plasma TMAO concentration is associated with NYHA class and adverse outcomes in heart failure patients (Tang et al., 2014; Tang et al., 2015b; Troseid et al., 2015). Moreover, higher level of TMAO is associated with increased risk of cardiovascular event in hemodialysis patients (Mafune et al., 2016; Shafi et al., 2016) and in patients with chronic kidney diseases (Kim et al., 2016). It has been suggested that TMAO leads to the development of atherosclerosis by suppressing reverse cholesterol transport through gut-microbiota-dependent mechanisms (Koeth et al., 2013). In addition, a recent study demonstrated that increased plasma TMAO concentration prolongs the hypertensive effect of angiotensin II, without affecting hemodynamics in normotensia (Ufnal et al., 2014). Nevertheless, the finding that the elevated concentration of plasma TMAO is associated with an increased risk of major adverse cardiovascular events (Koeth et al., 2013; Tang et al., 2013; Wang et al., 2011) cannot be

explained only by the proatherogenic properties of TMAO and angiotensin II regulation effect. Thus, whether TMAO is merely a biomarker or has direct effects on the progression of cardiovascular diseases remains unclear.

Recently, it has been shown that dietary TMAO worsens impaired glucose tolerance in high-fat diet-fed mice (Gao et al., 2014) and cardiac hypertrophy, dysfunction and fibrosis after transverse aortic constriction in an experimental model of heart failure (Organ et al., 2016). Moreover, the increased plasma TMAO concentration has been shown to be associated with diseases related to energy metabolism disorders, such as diabetes (Dambrova et al., 2016; Lever et al., 2014) and heart failure (Tang et al., 2015b; Troseid et al., 2015). Because heart function is highly dependent on energy derived from ATP that is generated during oxidative phosphorylation in mitochondria (Dzeja et al., 2000), the altered cardiac energy metabolism and mitochondrial dysfunction play crucial roles in the development of cardiovascular diseases (Fillmore and Lopaschuk, 2013; Singh et al., 2014). Therefore, we hypothesized that increased concentration of TMAO may alter mitochondrial energy metabolism. The aim of the present study was to determine the chronic and acute effects of TMAO on cardiac mitochondrial energy metabolism.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Animals and treatment

Twenty two male ICR mice at the age of 7 weeks weighing 20–25 g were obtained from Harlan Laboratories B.V. (Venray, Netherlands). Six male Wistar rats weighing 300–330 g were obtained from the Laboratory Animal Centre, University of Tartu (Tartu, Estonia). Experimental animals were housed under standard conditions (21-23°C, 12-hour light/dark cycle, relative humidity 45%-65%) with unlimited access to food (R70 diet, Lactamin AB, Kimstad, Sweden) and water. The experimental procedures were performed in accordance with the guidelines of the European Community and local laws and policies, and all of the procedures were approved by the Latvian Animal Protection Ethical Committee of the Food and Veterinary Service, Riga, Latvia (Food and Veterinary Service Ethical approval Nr.38, 01.01.2012.).

Ten mice were used to determine the acute effects of TMAO on mitochondrial energy metabolism. Mitochondria were isolated from cardiac tissues of rats and used as an enzyme source to determine the effects of TMAO on enzyme activity.

An additional 12 mice were randomly separated into two experimental groups that received water (Control) or TMAO at a dose of 120 mg/kg in the drinking water daily for 8 weeks. At the end of the treatment, mitochondrial respiration rates were determined in isolated saponin-permeabilized cardiac fibers. In addition, heart and plasma samples of these animals were immediately frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80°C for further analysis.

2.2.Determination of TMAO concentrations

Determination of TMAO concentrations in plasma and heart homogenate samples was performed by ultra-performance liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (UPLC/MS/MS) using a positive ion electrospray mode, as previously described (Dambrova et al., 2013; Grinberga et al., 2015).

2.3. Mitochondrial respiration measurements in the permeabilized cardiac fibers

The permeabilized cardiac fibers were prepared as previously described (Kuka et al., 2012) with some modifications. Briefly, bundles of fibers were permeabilized with 50 µg/mL saponin at 4°C for 15 minutes in buffer A (in mM: 20 imidazole, 0.5 dithiothreitol, 20 taurine, 7.1 MgCl₂, 50 MES, 5 ATP, 15 phosphocreatine, 2.6 CaK₂EGTA, 7.4 K₂EGTA, pH 7.0 at 0°C). The fibers were washed once for 15 minutes in buffer B (in mM: 20 imidazole, 0.5 dithiothreitol, 20 taurine, 1.6 MgCl₂, 100 MES, 3 KH₂PO₄, 2.95 CaK₂EGTA, 7.05 K₂EGTA, pH 7.1 at 4°C). Respiration measurements were performed at 37°C with a Clark-type electrode (Microelectrodes Inc., Bedford, USA) and Oxygraph-2k (O2k, OROBOROS Instruments, Innsbruck, Austria) in buffer B containing respiratory substrates. Pyruvate and malate (6+6 mM) were used to assess pyruvate metabolism-dependent LEAK (substrate dependent) respiration rate (complex I linked respiration). The ADP-stimulated respiration (OXPHOS state) was measured using 1 mM ADP. Succinate (10 mM) was added to reconstitute complex I & II (CI&II) linked respiration. Titration with the uncoupler, carbonyl cyanide m-chloro phenyl hydrazine (CCCP), (0.5–1 µM steps) was performed to determine electron transfer system (ETS) capacity. Rotenone (0.5 µM, inhibitor of complex I) and antimycin A (2.5 µM, inhibitor of complex III) were added to determine the CII-linked ETS capacity and residual oxygen consumption (ROX), respectively. Flux control ratios (FCR) were calculated by dividing respiration rates in all respiratory states by CI&II-linked ETS-capacity taken as a common reference state (Gnaiger, 2009). In addition, fatty acid oxidation was assessed at LEAK and OXPHOS states using 10 µM palmitoyl-CoA, 700 µM carnitine and 2 mM malate. Wet weight specific oxygen fluxes were compared after correction for ROX.

2.4. Determination of reactive oxygen species (ROS) production

ROS production as H₂O₂ flux was measured simultaneously with respirometry in the O2k-Fluorometer using the H₂O₂-sensitive probe Ampliflu™ Red (AmR) as described (Makrecka-Kuka et al., 2015). 10 μM AmR, 1 U/mL horse radish peroxidase and 5 U/mL superoxide dismutase were added to the chamber. H₂O₂ detection is based on the conversion of AmR into the fluorescent resorufin. Calibrations were performed with H₂O₂ repeatedly added at 0.1 μM steps. Volume-specific H₂O₂ fluxes were calculated in real-time from the positive time derivative of the resorufin signal over time (converted to H₂O₂ concentration based on the calibrations with H₂O₂).

2.5. Determination of enzyme activity

To determine pyruvate dehydrogenase (PDH) and carnitine palmitoyltransferase I (CPT I) activities, mitochondria from rat cardiac tissues were isolated as previously described (Kuka et al., 2012). PDH activity was spectrophotometrically determined in freshly isolated cardiac mitochondria as previously described (Ke et al., 2014). CPT I activity was assayed as the formation of radiolabeled palmitoyl-[³H]-carnitine from L-[N-methyl-³H] carnitine and palmitoyl-CoA as previously described (Berthon et al., 1998) with the modifications indicated below. For the reaction, 50 μM palmitoyl-CoA and 1 mM L-carnitine with 1 μCi L-[N-methyl-³H] carnitine (specific activity, 85 Ci/mmol, Biotrend, USA) were used. The reaction was performed at 30°C for 3 min and stopped by the addition of 1 M HCl. Samples were then centrifuged at 10000 g for 5 min at 4°C. The obtained pellet was suspended in water, and palmitoyl-[³H]-carnitine was extracted with water-saturated butanol. After centrifugation at 10000 g for 5 min at 4°C, an aliquot of the butanol phase was collected and counted for ³H using a scintillation cocktail.

2.6. Statistical analysis

The data are expressed as the mean ± standard error of the mean (SEM). For statistical analyses, Student's t-test or a one-way ANOVA with Dunnett's or Tukey's post-tests were

used. P values less than 0.05 were considered statistically significant. Statistical calculations were performed using Prism 5.03 software (GraphPad, San Diego, California, USA).

3. Results

3.1. The effects of TMAO on cardiac mitochondrial function

To determine whether TMAO affects mitochondrial function, mitochondrial respiration measurements were performed in the absence or presence of TMAO at a concentration of 20 μ M, as found in mice cardiac tissues after 1 h of single intraperitoneal administration of TMAO at a dose of 100 mg/kg (data not shown). The respiration rates in the LEAK and OXPHOS states with pyruvate+malate were decreased by 47 and 34%, respectively, in the presence of 20 μ M TMAO in the respiration medium (Fig. 1A). In addition, administration of 20 μ M TMAO inhibited LEAK respiration with palmitoyl-CoA by 24%, but did not affect OXPHOS respiration (Fig. 1B). The observed 28% decrease in CI&II linked OXPHOS respiration induced by TMAO can be explained by the reduction in CI-linked respiration (OXPHOS state with pyruvate+malate as substrates) (Fig. 1C). The addition of 20 μ M TMAO to the respiration medium did not induce any changes in ETS capacity and CII-linked ETS respiration states. Moreover, flux control ratios were not affected by TMAO (Fig. 1D). Taken together, these results demonstrate that TMAO directly induces disturbances in cardiac energy metabolism by inhibiting pyruvate and fatty acid oxidation, but does not affect mitochondrial electron transfer system.

Additional measurements of enzyme activity showed that TMAO partially reduces PDH activity in isolated cardiac mitochondria (Fig. 2A), indicating impaired pyruvate flux via PDH. The CPT I activity measurements demonstrated that the TMAO-induced decrease in respiration with palmitoyl-CoA is not CPT I-dependent (Fig. 2B). These results indicate that

TMAO-induced impairment in mitochondrial energy metabolism could be related to the simultaneous inhibition of pyruvate flux and β -oxidation.

3.2. The effects of TMAO on mitochondrial ROS production

To determine whether TMAO affects mitochondrial ROS production, H_2O_2 flux measurements were performed in the absence or presence of TMAO at a concentration of 20 μ M at different coupling states. The H_2O_2 flow rates in LEAK, OXPHOS and CI&II-linked ETS states were similar between groups (Fig. 3A). The higher H_2O_2 flow and H_2O_2/O_2 ratio were observed in CII-linked ETS state in the presence of 20 μ M TMAO (Fig. 3), however there was no statistically significant difference between groups. These results indicate that TMAO does not affect mitochondrial ROS production under physiological conditions.

3.3. The chronic effects of TMAO on cardiac mitochondrial energy metabolism

In order to determine whether the observed acute TMAO effects on mitochondrial energy metabolism can be translated to the long-term exposure to the increased TMAO levels, the concentration of TMAO and mitochondrial respiration with pyruvate+malate and palmitoyl-CoA were measured after administration of TMAO at a dose of 120 mg/kg for 8 weeks. TMAO treatment for 8 weeks did not affect water intake (data not shown). Body weight at the end of experiment was similar between groups (41.1 ± 0.6 vs 41.6 ± 1.6 g). As shown in Fig. 4A, TMAO treatment resulted in a significant 23-fold increase in the concentration of TMAO in the plasma from 0.66 ± 0.04 to 15.4 ± 3.7 μ M compared to the control group. The TMAO concentration in cardiac tissue in the TMAO-treated group was 11.6 ± 1.8 nmol/g, which was 22-fold higher than that of the control group (Fig. 4B). After long-term TMAO administration, LEAK respiration rate with pyruvate+malate was reduced by 30%, but OXPHOS respiration was not altered (Fig. 4C). Long-term TMAO administration significantly decreased the mitochondrial respiration rate in both LEAK and OXPHOS states by 36% when palmitoyl-CoA was used as a respiratory substrate (Fig. 4D).

Overall, these results indicate that long-term increased TMAO concentration induces disturbances in cardiac mitochondrial energy metabolism.

4. Discussion

We have examined the effects of TMAO on energy metabolism processes in cardiac mitochondria. Our results demonstrate that TMAO reduces both pyruvate and fatty acid oxidation in cardiac mitochondria. TMAO reduces substrate flux via PDH and impairs β -oxidation that can lead to insufficient energy production in the cardiac cell. Taken together, our results provide evidence that increased TMAO concentrations can be a cause of cardiovascular diseases dependent on energy metabolism disorders such as heart failure.

Cardiac mitochondria produce energy from both pyruvate and fatty acids, and the ability to switch between available substrates is essential for cell functioning (Fillmore and Lopaschuk, 2013; van de Weijer et al., 2013). Increased TMAO concentration reduced both pyruvate and fatty acid oxidation, without affecting ETS capacity. Because long-term TMAO administration decreases oxidative phosphorylation-dependent mitochondrial respiration with palmitoyl-CoA, but not with pyruvate, TMAO does not induce mitochondrial electron transport system dysfunction, but acts directly on fatty acid oxidation, the PDH complex and/or the Krebs cycle. TMAO does not inhibit citrate synthase (data not shown), the rate-determining enzyme of the Krebs cycle (Walsh et al., 1987); therefore, the Krebs cycle processes are not affected by TMAO. Because TMAO does not inhibit CPT I, it can be concluded that TMAO limits fatty acid oxidation due to direct inhibition of β -oxidation. In addition, TMAO partially inhibits substrate flux via PDH. Taken together, the present results demonstrate that TMAO induces mitochondrial energy metabolism dysfunction by inhibiting β -oxidation and PDH.

As a biomarker, TMAO concentration is increased in patients with heart failure and is associated with the progression of disease (Troseid et al., 2015). Moreover, it has recently

been demonstrated that dietary TMAO worsens heart failure in an experimental mouse model (Organ et al., 2016); however, the direct role and mechanism of action of TMAO in the progression of heart failure have never been investigated. It has been shown that glucose oxidation is reduced due to impaired substrate flux via PDH in heart failure (Kato et al., 2010; Mori et al., 2012). In addition, decrease in the cardiac fatty acid oxidation rate induces the onset and progression of heart failure (Doenst et al., 2010; Osorio et al., 2002; Sack et al., 1996). In the present study, TMAO was found to induce reduction of fatty acid oxidation and partially inhibit energy production from pyruvate. These data indicate that TMAO could be at least partially responsible for reduced fatty acid and glucose utilization in the failing heart. Overall, because energy metabolism impairment is one of the leading mechanisms underlying the progression of heart failure (Doenst et al., 2013; Wang et al., 2014), the present finding that TMAO directly impairs mitochondrial energy metabolism links the development and progression of heart failure to the increased concentration of TMAO.

Previously, it has been shown that dietary TMAO exposure in mice leads to the progression of renal fibrosis (Tang et al., 2015a). Moreover, in recent study the enhanced myocardial fibrosis was observed after long-term TMAO supplementation in the animal model of heart failure (Organ et al., 2016). Moreover, Since increased ROS production contributes to the progression of fibrosis (Richter and Kietzmann, 2016), TMAO could increase mitochondrial ROS production and, thus, enhance progression of fibrosis and heart failure. Our results demonstrate that TMAO does not affect ROS production in cardiac mitochondria under physiological conditions. In contrast, it has been shown that long-term administration of 1.5% TMAO in drinking water induces oxidative stress in liver tissues (Hu et al., 2015); however, the concentrations of TMAO in the plasma and tissues were not determined. Thus, it cannot be concluded that the observed oxidative damage of the liver directly depends on TMAO content in tissues. In our study the observed decrease in LEAK

state mitochondrial respiration with both pyruvate and palmitoyl-CoA after TMAO administration indicates that the flux of NADH produced from pyruvate and fatty acid metabolism through CI is partially reduced. Since the inhibition of CI stimulates ROS formation (Fato et al., 2009), it cannot be excluded that TMAO could exacerbate mitochondrial ROS production under pathological conditions due to reduction of NADH flux through CI. Taken together, the data suggest that TMAO does not directly stimulate mitochondrial ROS production and additional factors are necessary to provoke oxidative stress, which can be enhanced by increased TMAO concentration.

The concentration of TMAO highly varies intra-individually, and it is strongly affected by dietary habits and the composition of intestinal microbiota (Kuhn et al., 2016). The plasma concentration of TMAO found in controls without cardiometabolic diseases varies from 1 μM to 7.9 μM and is about 3 μM in average (Kuhn et al., 2016; Mueller et al., 2015; Troseid et al., 2015). It has been demonstrated that heart failure patients with TMAO concentration above 6.1-8.5 μM have higher risk of future adverse cardiac events (Tang et al., 2014; Tang et al., 2015b). Moreover, the higher concentration of TMAO found in plasma of heart failure patients is associated with the greater severity of disease and it is about 13 μM in patients diagnosed for the New York Heart Association (NYHA) class III/IV (Troseid et al., 2015). Interestingly, even a 100-fold increase in plasma TMAO concentration (from 0.6 μM to 60 μM) did not induce any effects on hemodynamic parameters in rats (Ufnal et al., 2014). Moreover, the administration of 0.12% TMAO in standard chow for 3 weeks did not induce any changes in cardiac function in mice (Organ et al., 2016). However, after transverse aortic constriction the administration of TMAO for additional 12 weeks increased TMAO concentration in the plasma 15-fold (from 1.7 μM to 25.2 μM) and accelerated the progression of heart failure (Organ et al., 2016). In our study, after 8 weeks of TMAO administration the plasma concentration of TMAO was about 15 μM , similar to concentration

found in heart failure patients with high risk of adverse cardiovascular events, and was associated with partial disturbances in cardiac mitochondrial energy metabolism. Taken together, data suggest that TMAO acts as an additional risk factor that promotes the progression of heart failure rather than directly causes the disease.

Although we observed a TMAO-induced impairment of mitochondrial energy metabolism, it has never been reported that TMAO *per se* would alter cardiac function. In contrary, the protective role of TMAO in the reduction of deleterious effects of oxidative stress was reported previously (Lupachyk et al., 2013; Ufnal et al., 2015). As in our study TMAO treatment reduced the efficiency of mitochondrial energy metabolism, we can hypothesize that TMAO may induce a mild metabolic stress and result in a preconditioning-like effect. This suggestion may also explain the benefits of the TMAO-rich seafood consumption in the primary prevention of cardiovascular diseases (Aadland et al., 2015; Tektonidis et al., 2015). Altogether, further studies are necessary to determine whether TMAO possesses a preconditioning-like effect on the cardiovascular system. However, it should be noted that TMAO-impaired mitochondrial energy metabolism could exacerbate the progression of already present cardiovascular disease.

In conclusion, our results demonstrate that TMAO impairs both pyruvate and fatty acid oxidation in cardiac mitochondria. Thus, the increased content of TMAO in cardiac tissues reduces the efficiency of energy production in the cardiac tissues that can lead to cardiac remodeling and the progression of heart failure.

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Conflict of interest

Authors have no conflict of interests.

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Figures

Fig. 1. The acute effects of TMAO on mitochondrial respiration rate measurements in cardiac fibers using different substrates. TMAO (20 μ M) decreases substrate-dependent (LEAK) respiration rate and ADP-stimulated (OXPHOS) respiration with pyruvate (A). TMAO (20 μ M) decreases LEAK, but does not affect OXPHOS respiration when palmitoyl-CoA is used as a substrate (B). TMAO (20 μ M) slightly decreases complex I & II (CI&II) linked OXPHOS respiration without affecting electron transfer system (ETS) capacity (C) and flux control ratios (D). The results are presented as the average values \pm SEM of 6-8 independent measurements. * indicates a significant difference from the control group (Student's t-test, $P < 0.05$).

Fig. 2. The effects of TMAO on the activity of enzymes involved in mitochondrial energy metabolism. TMAO partially inhibits pyruvate dehydrogenase (PDH) (A), but does not affect carnitine palmitoyltransferase I (CPT I) activity (B). The results are presented as the average values \pm SEM of 3-5 independent measurements. * indicates a significant difference from the control measurement (Dunnett's test, $P < 0.05$).

Fig. 3. Coupling state-specific mitochondrial ROS production in cardiac fibers in the presence of TMAO. TMAO (20 μM) has no effect on H₂O₂ flow (A) or H₂O₂/O ratio (B). The results are presented as the average values ± SEM of 5-6 independent measurements.

Fig. 4. The effects of long-term TMAO administration at a dose of 120 mg/kg for 8 weeks on TMAO concentration and mitochondrial energy metabolism in cardiac fibers. Long-term administration of TMAO significantly increases TMAO concentration in plasma (A) and cardiac tissues (B). Administration of TMAO decreases substrate-dependent (LEAK) respiration rate without affecting ADP-stimulated (OXPHOS) respiration with pyruvate (C). The LEAK and OXPHOS respiration rates with palmitoyl-CoA were decreased after long-term TMAO administration (D). The results are presented as the average values \pm SEM of 6 animals. * indicates a significant difference from the control group (Student's t-test, $P < 0.05$).